

This is not a watch. Reframing the design of wrist-worn devices

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Abstract Various types of wrist-worn devices are increasingly introduced as consumer products in our daily life. However, most of these devices are framed as *a watch* regardless of their different purposes and contexts of use. This paper reflects on the design of current wrist-worn devices and reframes their meanings with an aim to inform and inspire further design explorations. We conducted a trend survey by reviewing articles about consumer wearable design and technology from popular online press and student design explorations. The insights from the trend survey and the design explorations are synthesized to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design *in the wild* and *in a design studio context*. Based on the insights from both approaches, we propose varied meanings of wrist-worn devices in relation to corresponding formal and technological components. The meanings include 1) tracker for making sense of personal behaviors and situations, 2) controller for streamlining interactions across connected devices with unique affordance and style, 3) notification manager for prompting follow-up actions with minimal distraction, and 4) statement for lifestyle changes and goal achievement. Based on the proposed framework, further design and research implications are discussed toward connected and mediated human experience with augmented digital systems.

Keywords *Wearable devices, Wrist-worn devices, Forms, Meanings, Design-driven approaches*

Introduction

Forms and meanings of recent digital products have become diversified according to technological development and lifestyle changes. Digital devices are no longer limited to flat screen-based forms for supporting work-related tasks but expanded to flexible and embedded forms for assisting a wide range of personal activities including fitness, leisure and communication. Wearable is one of the largely emerging forms of digital devices, and new applications and systems under this category have been increasingly introduced, influencing on broader ecosystems of other digital devices and related services. Wrist-worn devices are one of the representative forms of wearable products today. While their potential in new user experiences and business opportunities seems to be promising, their design space has not been fully explored yet when it comes to their creative forms and meanings (Xu & Lyons, 2015). The market is saturated in a sense with too many similar types of devices—mostly in forms of fitness tracking wristbands or notice alerting smartwatches, and the marriage between technology and fashion in the design of these devices is still in its experimental stage, although its importance is being more seriously considered. The growing number of wrist worn digital devices brings back the battle between the traditional watch industry and the information technology industry from early 1980's,

raising tensions between electronic and mechanical components, and between technology-driven and craft-oriented approaches in watch design (Thompson, 2015).

Regardless of their growing number and technical capabilities, wrist wearable devices are still a new product category; and in most cases people do not know what to expect from them and what to use them for (Pizza, Brown, McMillan & Lampinen, 2016). There have been studies that investigate possible meanings, forms and use cases of wrist-worn digital devices based on familiar use cases of analogue watches (Lyons, 2015). Although such frame of watch may facilitate the design and use of new wearable devices with the reference of familiar forms and meanings, digital products could do far more and the semantic frame of wristband or smartwatch could limit creative approaches to wearable devices. In addition, the current design of wristbands or smartwatches is largely pushed by technology and market opportunities, not yet fully leveraging aesthetic and experiential potentials of wearable media and interaction technology (Pederson, 2013). We argue that there is a need for reflecting on trending issues about the design of wrist worn devices in order to speculate on yet-unexplored meanings and forms of these devices with greater impacts on user experience. This study, taking a critical stance to technology-driven

approaches to consumer wearable devices, reflects on their deeper meanings and purposes of use based on our survey of recent design trends and case studies of design explorations. By doing so, we aim to reconceptualize the design of wrist-worn devices and to propose a reflective framework, which could better inform and inspire design-driven explorations to this category of devices. Specific methods and objectives of this study follow in the next section.

Methods and objectives

This paper reflects on issues and approaches related to the design of wrist-worn devices with a focus on their meanings and forms. First, we conducted a trend survey by reviewing articles about wearable design, technology and business from popular online press in order to get a sense of what types of wrist-worn devices exist, how they are marketed, and which elements are involved in their design beyond form-making. In parallel, we also conducted student design explorations as studio projects to investigate detailed formal elements of and related design approaches to wearable applications, followed by a debrief session about the project outcomes and processes. The survey and design explorations were not planned to inform each other from the beginning. Instead of applying or proving insights from one to the other, we intended to compare “real world” issues about the design of wrist-worn devices in practice and “design-focused” issues that are directly related to concept development and form-making process. By conducting the two studies separately, we aim to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design *in the wild* and *in a design studio context*. In the end, we synthesize the insights from the two studies to sort through challenges and opportunities in further design explorations of wrist worn devices in relation with other digital systems.

The insights from the trend survey and design explorations are summarized in the following sections, put in *an innovation matrix* in the end. The innovation matrix was devised by Verganti (2009) to map out a trajectory of various meanings of a category of products in relation to different technologies associated with each meaning. According to Verganti, product innovations happen in two dimensions: *development of new technology* (i.e., faster processing speed, smaller size, cheaper cost, efficient engineering solutions) and *discovery of new meanings* (i.e., product values, user experiences). He argues that the former is considered as engineering-driven innovation, while the later as truly design-driven innovation. The discovery of new meaning, supported by corresponding technology, expands design opportunities by adding new values to market and user experience, as seen in many design cases (e.g., Alessi Anna G. Corkscrew that shifted meanings of wine openers from a kitchen gadget to a playful artifact, Nintendo Wii remote controller with motion sensor that shifted meanings of video games from a computer graphical experience to a bodily experience). Later on, *radical innovation in meaning* is further discussed in Norman and Verganti (2014) as an alternative perspective to currently dominant User-Centered Design (UCD) approaches, which they argue

mostly result in *incremental improvements* of product features based on observed user needs or problems. Instead, radical innovation results from *technology epiphany* through the discovery of quiescent meanings as forward looking approach to design. Although the process is not as straightforward as incremental design improvement (that is grounded on structured user research or evaluation), technology epiphany does not come by chance either. It requires critical and rigorous design discourse by considering psychological and cultural dimensions of being human including values, beliefs, norms and traditions. The role of designers as *interpreter* is emphasized to synthesize all relevant issues and trends into deeper insights and to create *an object as a proposal* by envisioning new values.

As a foundation for such discovery and proposal of new meanings, in what follows, we map out technological and sociocultural issues revealed from our trend research and synthesize them with the insights from our design explorations. Under our main goal to reflect and reframe the design of wrist-worn devices, specific objectives of this paper include 1) investigating their meanings in broader product ecology, 2) identifying their form factors in relation to their meanings, and 3) speculating how design-driven approaches could come into the scene where many conflicting constraints coexist.

Survey of trending issues about wrist-worn devices

As an initial attempt to get a sense of existing products and relevant design issues in practice, we reviewed articles about wearable design published in technology, fashion, lifestyle and business magazines as well as design blogs (i.e., The Atlantic, The Economist, Fast Company, Wired, Fashion Nerd, Creative Applications, Mashable, Visual News) by subscribing them over 3 months (May – August, 2015), archiving the articles specific to “wearables” and further investigating products and projects mentioned in those articles. In addition, we looked into crowdfunding websites including Kickstarter and Indiegogo to take new start-up projects into account, and also attended Wearable Technologies Conference (July 9-10 2015 in San Francisco), which hosted wearable product showcases, platform/solution demonstrations, and panel discussions on facing issues in wearable industry. From all these sources, related design cases that share similar technology or business issues are selected and categorized into trends. In what follows, four selected trends are highlighted, each of which corresponds to different meanings and formal and technological components of wrist-worn devices.

Trending issue 1: activity and/or mood tracker

Thanks to advanced information and sensor technology, tracking and monitoring personal data has become widely available as consumer wearable devices. Fitness trackers are one of the most popular forms of wearable devices today. Their meanings and functions are largely grounded on the notion of *quantified self*, which views a personal life as an integral of quantitatively measurable activities (The

Economist, 2013). Beyond tracking activities in real time, the notion is expanded to prompt self-reflection on accumulated patterns or noticeable changes of personal behaviors over time, enabling individuals to better know about themselves and even to experiment with different personal strategies in managing their life activities. With common technical features of tracking movement (e.g., steps, postures) or health condition (e.g., heart rate), product meanings could vary depending on different marketing strategies and intended experiential values, ranging from *activity tracker* or *health monitor* (e.g., Fitbit) to *fitness companion* or *personal coach* (e.g., MOOV: multi-sport wearable coach) as well as to *mood tracker* (e.g., Sona: bracelet for mind and body wellness, Embrace Watch: stress monitoring watch, myfeel: wristband that recognizes emotions). We have observed that attempts are increasing to infer mood or emotional conditions by synthesizing activity, physiological and contextual data and manual logs.

While compact size and minimal interface design (both in terms of inputs and displays) are general design considerations for such tracking devices, variations of materials and unique styles are experimented as a point of difference based on the brand strategy of each device. In addition, there are immense design opportunities being discussed for mobile apps, which work in connection with wrist-worn tracking devices. Mobile apps play a crucial role in guiding self-reflection through simple visualizations of behavioral patterns and streamlined interactions for achieving goals with engaging visual incentives based on cognitive behavioral therapy.

Trending issue 2: smartwatch

The design of wrist-worn devices needs to be understood in the context of digital ecosystems where multiple devices—including mobile phones, consumer and home electronic devices, and automotive devices—cooperatively interact with each other by sharing information and functionality across them (Levy, 2015). Within complex digital ecosystems, devices serve as a set of *endpoints* to access applications and information archived in the cloud or to interact with people, social communities and businesses beyond the scope of personal activities. Personal, social and environmental data captured through the device mesh will construct dynamic digital information ecosystems and model users' behavior journeys to facilitate the delivery of apps and services according to their contexts. Smartwatch, one of the representative types of wearable devices, serves as a platform for quickly accessing, managing and updating information from other devices, involving with more active and complex interactions than passive trackers to navigate through different apps and information states built in them. Unique forms and affordances of interfaces for specific tasks could be sacrificed to accommodate different purposes in one device. A wrist has become an even more rare estate for wearable devices due to the competition between versatile smartwatches and single-purpose devices.

Meanings of smartwatches and purposes for using them are multifaceted compared to those of single-

purpose activity trackers due to their versatile features and use cases. A recent study reports that Apple Watch since released in 2015 has been mostly used to check *time*, *activity data*, and *notifications* (Pizza, Brown, McMillan & Lampinen, 2016). Although these main uses are not surprising or exciting, the study discusses implications about deeper meanings behind checking time and activity records in terms of proactive personal schedule or goal management. Checking notifications is considered as *triage* of incoming messages or emails from other devices to reduce their interruptions in other foreground tasks. With increasing technology capabilities and broadening application areas, the meanings of smartwatches are evolving to be more deeply involved in our daily routines, reshaping broader ecosystems of digital and physical devices (Bernaerts et al., 2015).

Trending issue 3: fashionable tech

With their increasing capabilities and intimacy, wearable devices nowadays do not only serve as utilitarian artifacts but also display their sociocultural values and personal tastes as fashion items. However, regardless of the growing use of fitness trackers or smartwatches, still they are rather considered as digital gadgets than fashion accessories, not experienced as part of a complete outfit (Kessler, 2015). Styles and aesthetic expressions are as critical considerations as technical features and usability in the design and use of wearable devices. Different design approaches and inspirations are searched for from fashion studies to complement current digital product design where user-centered approaches are dominant (Pan and Stolterman, 2015). On the contrary to such utilitarian, problem-driven design approaches, fashion design is driven by continuous changes and possibilities, intentionally creating new values and variations, reflecting (and often leading) emerging lifestyles (Juhlin, 2015). In this regard, sociocultural perspectives of styles and economic values of materials are also important design factors to consider in addition to technical and functional features of wearable devices, and wearable design requires truly multi-disciplinary expertise and methodology more than any other consumer product categories (Raj & Ha-Brookshire, 2015). The marriage between fashion and technology is constantly experimented in practice through collaborations between high-end fashion brands and/or designers and information technology companies, for example, by applying new styles or materials to the exterior of digital devices (e.g., Apple Watch Hermès) or by embedding technical features into fashion and jewelry that are already a big part of our life (e.g., making payments with clothing introduced by Friedman, 2015; illuminated uniform for communication among flight crew introduced by Pakhchyan, 2015). These fashion-driven approaches are radical in a sense that they turn down the mantra of form follows function in modern product design by putting function into seemingly irrelevant forms of existing artifacts. Through radical approaches to digital product design, current forms of digital devices, which consist of discrete input and display interfaces, could be further *deconstructed* and *realigned* into new interactive experience embedded in fashion.

Trending issue 4: creative and critical exploration

Besides already widely used consumer products, new concepts for wrist-worn devices are continuously introduced by start-ups, research labs and creative individuals, proposing new meanings and forms for wrist-worn devices with new device features and shapes (e.g., Kapture: audio recording wristband that looks like a retro microphone), band and display materials (e.g., analogue activity tracker that employs insoluble liquids as display materials, designed by Vanhemert, 2015), display interfaces (e.g., smartwatch display customized to visualize football match results, introduced in Cool Wearable, 2014), and multi-sensory interactions (e.g., Doppel - pace setting wristband through vibration; Arduino wearable prototypes introduced in Einarson, 2013; Ahn et al, 2015). Thanks to more accessible prototyping technologies including 3D printer and electronic circuit printer as well as popularized social platforms for crowdfunding, it has become relatively easier to turn ideas into prototypes. However, the translation from a prototype to a product is still challenging due to too many competitors, social and government regulations in health data tracking and interventions, and common technical constraints in terms of battery or platform for device network, most of which are not necessarily direct design problems from a particular perspective concerning on forms and meanings. Although technical constraints and regulations in the real world should not be ignored in design, at least sorting through which factors could be further explored from a design-oriented approach would shed light on more meaningful areas for future design research and education. Recently there are increasing creative and critical initiatives in design research to envision the future of technology and human life by provoking and reframing problems beyond solving given ones: for example, as seen in the notions of *slow technology* that promotes the use of technology for reflection (vs. for productivity) (Hallnäs & Redström, 2011), *grounded innovation* that experiments applications of new technology by developing unique use cases with marginalized or pioneering user groups (Holmquist, 2012), *concept-driven interaction* design that proposes a theoretically and historically grounded approach to develop innovative design concepts (Stolterman & Wiberg, 2010), and *speculative design* that brings fiction as a means of provoking social visions (Dunne & Raby, 2013). These alternative approaches for creative and critical design explorations are also in demand to support design-driven innovation in wearable design.

Showcase of design explorations from studio projects

This section describes our design explorations conducted as two studio courses in the School of Design at University of Cincinnati: one with seniors (Fall, 2014) and the other with first year masters (Spring, 2014). Both studios aimed to explore unique forms and meanings of wearable devices based on research, use case development and iterative prototyping. Research activities included survey of emerging social, cultural and technology trends as well as literature review and primary research about

chosen user groups and contexts. In terms of prototyping, paper and foam board mock-ups were employed at earlier phases; 3D renderings and screen mockups were mostly used to specify formal details; and electronic prototyping with Arduino was also used optionally to test conceptual or technical feasibility of proposed concepts. While the senior studio focused on formal development and refinement for branding and manufacturing details, the graduate studio emphasized conceptual explorations of speculative wearable systems.

The senior studio was carried out as an interdisciplinary design course with 18 enrolled students from industrial, communication and fashion design programs across 15 weeks. Students collaboratively conducted trend research about emerging technology and social issues to identify particular situations where wearable technology could be introduced with promising opportunities, and explored unique forms to address and/or resolve their focused design problems. The project brief did not specify to design wrist-worn devices, but three out of five team projects in total were turned out to be wrist wearable (Figure 1: Echo, Figure 2: Audapt, Figure 4: Cue) with one glove type device (Figure 5: Gro) and one clip type device for bike signaling.

The graduate course was carried out as independent studio projects across 15 weeks with 6 students, all of whom have their background in industrial or communication design. Students conducted literature review about contemporary communication culture with wearable media technology, and each took on a concept for individual project to leverage experiential potentials of embodied digital media. One project out of five in total was turned out to be wrist wearable (Figure 3: Squeezing Bracelet) with the other four were presented as conceptual systems connected and embedded in other objects or environments (Figure 6 – 8: smart shoes, spikey mobile phone cover, alarming pillow, haptic GPS navigation gloves, and gaming t-shirt).

In what follows, we introduce three selected projects of wrist-worn devices to showcase their design processes in terms of how detail form factors and interfaces have been explored and integrated with specific use cases.

Project 1. Echo: the modern yodel

Echo is a communication device for snowboarders, who need to navigate and connect to remotely located team members on the mountain. To resolve their hassles of taking out a mobile phone from their pocket and manipulating its touch screen with their fingers out of gloves, it proposes a *rotate-and-press* interface solution, which is integrated into the physical frame around the digital screen, making it easy to manipulate by holding and pressing the frame still with their gloves on their hands. The screen interface and navigation are simplified to accommodate the rotate-and-press manipulation with the frame. The frame does not only solve the concerned problem in use, but also adds a bold and bulky style to the device, which properly communicates its intended use.

Figure 1. Echo with rotate-and-press interface (Design by Mitch Bernarding, Jennifer Beruscha, Seth Gillepe and Katarina Jung).

Figure 2. Audapt with swipe-and-tap interface (Design by Jay Jansen, Jon Riehle, Julie Morycz and Trent Victor).

Project 2. Audapt: the hearing controller

Audapt is a hearing aid system that consists of a hearing aid piece, a mobile app, and a wrist-worn controller. Hearing aids are usually hard to adjust, uncomfortable, and carry a stigma with their often-unsightly appearance. To make them easy to control and fashionable, a mobile app and a wrist controller are proposed as primary and secondary controllers. The four lights on the wrist controller correspond to four hearing presets customized in the mobile app, and can be switched by swiping left and right on the indented interface of the device. Tapping each end of the interface module adjusts volume. This interface solution was detailed after iterative sketches of different display face shapes and arrangements of input and output interfaces, most of which quite looked like a regular watch. It has been a main design issue for this team to make the device *not-looking-like-watch*, and they came up with a simpler interface solution than regular watch faces by integrating inputs and outputs with minimal hints of visual affordance for swiping and tapping and display lights.

Project 3. Squeezing bracelet

Squeezing bracelet is a conceptual wearable device that reminds of tasks to be completed in connection with a scheduler mobile app. Five tasks can be added to a daily to-do list with specific due times set in the mobile app, and each task is represented in distinct lights on the bracelet. If a task is not checked out by its due time, the bracelet will give a reminder by blinking its corresponding light and being continuously squeezed as time passes. The concept is rather a critical statement than a practical solution by expressing our obsession with productivity through its unpleasant look-and-feel like a handcuff and corresponding physical punishment.

Debrief of design processes and outcomes

In addition to regular studio critique sessions and observations throughout these design explorations, a focus group was conducted with four volunteering students to debrief design processes and outcomes. Although not all concepts proposed from the design exploration are conceptually or technically innovative,

Figure 3. Squeezing Bracelet: sketch and rendered images (Design by Soojin Kim).

Figure 4. Cue: modular clip for managing notifications (Design by Kyle Bennett, Minsun Hong, Chelsey Burgess and Tom Pietzsch).

each of the projects showcases a unique form-making process by illustrating how detail form factors and interface solutions are explored and integrated with specific meanings of their use cases. One of the frequently mentioned challenges in the form explorations was to make a wrist-worn device *not looking like a watch*. Just because of the basic formal structure consisting of a display face and a band, their designed device was easily considered as a watch during critiques, and thus their intended design problems and solutions were not successfully communicated at the beginning. Focusing on particular problems and interactive tasks helped them *deconstruct* the watch structure and come up with simple but unique interface forms. At the same time, a compact device size was definitely a critical constraint in exploring diverse formal structures and integrating complex interactive features. However, as most design solutions were developed in connection with mobile apps, the problem with limited interface and display surface was partly resolved by using larger screen of smartphones. The pair of a wrist-worn device and a mobile app has become a common product system with the wrist-worn device in charge of passive data tracking and quick access to selected features and the app in charge of complex information visualization and navigation. Lastly, some interactive aspects of proposed concepts were experimented in electronic prototyping by using Arduino in order to test their conceptual and technical validity, for example, in the case of Squeezing Bracelet, a tightening structure was tested with a micro motor controlled by a mobile app

via Bluetooth. However, it was challenging to demonstrate such wireless communication between multiple devices compared to its reward in terms of exploration and evaluation of initial concepts. Too much technical knowledge and experiments were required for designers without engineering background to demonstrate a customized pairing of multiple devices, while using a ready-made toolkit is limiting design explorations. In spite of this challenge, interactive prototyping was still helpful to *experience* a proposed design scenario, especially to simulate initial interaction flows of embedded systems where tangible or visible formal elements are not clear.

There are also other forms of wearable devices explored beside wrist-wearables, including a modular clip for displaying notifications from a smartphone (Figure 4: Cue), a lighting module for bikers to communicate turn signals with hand gestures, a gardening glove that measures soil conditions for beginners (Figure 5: Gro), haptic GPS navigation gloves (Figure 6: JA), a spiky mobile phone cover that prevents it from being held or used in bedtime (Figure 7), an alarm pillow that vibrates in the morning, vibrating shoes that encourage working out, a t-shirt for playing a mobile phone game by sending vibration messages through a wirelessly connected t-shirt (Figure 8: Salmon). These different forms of design concepts still illustrate a common user expectation for interactive applications that goes beyond wearable forms by connecting various digital or physical objects to assist human activities and augment human

Figure 5. Gro: smart gardening glove for on-site soil testing and recording (Design by El-Asa Crawford, Jacklyn Crofts and Shirley Yip).

Figure 6. JA: haptic GPS navigation gloves (Design by Soojin Kim).

Figure 7. A spiky mobile phone cover that prevents it from being held at night (Design by Yanhan Li).

Figure 8. Salmon: vibrating t-shirt connected to a mobile game (Design by Bennett Nestok and Patrick Fitzgerald).

abilities through *proactive data tracking* and its *proper representation*, which will be further discussed in the next section.

Reflection: if not a watch, then what is it?

The selected design cases above illustrate how particular needs or problems identified from research have been resolved in unique forms of interfaces through systematic formal explorations. Different parts of wrist-worn devices (e.g., displays—either visual or tactile, frames around display faces, bands, and other peripheral devices) could be developed or combined into new formal structures, interface components, and aesthetic styles. Regarding our initial argument about the need for alternative conceptual frames of wrist-worn devices, we reflect on what else they could mean by deconstructing their functional and experiential design elements. In the innovation matrix (Table 1), the four meanings emerged from our trend survey and design explorations are listed on the x-axis and mapped to related technological components on the y-axis,

constructing varied conceptual frames described below. The proposed frames are by no means mutually exclusive or definitive. Instead, they are meant to be continuously expanded and combined through further design explorations.

Frame 1: Tracker for making sense of personal behaviors and situations

As reviewed in the trend survey, diverse human activities can be tracked with more compact but accurate sensors, and the interpretation and representation of tracked data has become a significant design concern to guide self-reflection through engaging interaction prompts (Sanches, 2000). While tracking technology and relevant studies about quantified self have opened up a new design space for personal fitness and health management through wearable devices (Wallack 2015), it should be noted that not all human activities are quantifiable; trackable data represents only part of human life; and too much data could add more cognitive fatigue, if not properly synthesized (Bumgardner, 2015; Wagstaff,

2015). More complex factors are involved in a personal life including social, emotional and environmental conditions beyond physical activities. Especially emotional awareness has become a more important subject in the contemporary society with increasing cognitive load from digital devices and various information sources, and commercial interest and technological capabilities for emotional tracking and mood changing are further growing. However, this area has been rarely approached in our studio projects, and our assumption is: as such design opportunities largely rely on data analytics, it was hard to develop new concepts of data tracking and synthesis without already collected set of data or proper design tools to play with it. Not only passive tracking, but also proactive user reflections on their tracked behavioral data need to be considered as a whole cycle of user experience, and corresponding theoretical and technical support is in need for design explorations. In addition, creative interpretations of bodily interactions beyond counting steps or tracking locations could be further explored in relation to their effects on our physical and social life (Johnson, 2008; Höök et al., 2015). Specifically, the concept of *lived body*, the interconnected relationships between human perception and action in physical and social context (Svanæs, 2013), could be expanded with connected data tracking system to make better sense of our environment as well as to make optimal decisions for actions with less cognitive effort (Dijk, Lugt & Hummels, 2014).

Frame 2: Controller for streamlining interaction with unique affordance and style

As evident both in the trend related to smartwatches and our design explorations, most wrist-worn devices are used as a secondary controller to quickly access selected features or data from other devices connected within digital ecosystems. Thanks to the development of short-range, ad hoc networking technologies, a digital ecosystem could be more fluidly expanded and assembled with multiple devices (Jung et al. 2010), and a mobile app usually serves as a default platform to set up and navigate complex information in

connection with a wrist-worn device. Design opportunities in this frame have been most actively explored in our design projects, especially in terms of developing unique forms, styles and interfaces of wrist-worn devices. While the design of wrist-worn controllers is supposed to be simple and minimal in terms of their forms, they also should correspond to the interaction flow and navigation hierarchy of other devices and applications connected within their system in order to support streamlined user experience across them. Specifically, types of information, related interaction tasks, and navigation structure behind a controller device should be carefully crafted into proper interface forms to represent their affordance and ergonomics. As seen in the cases of Echo and Audapt, successful interface solutions of a simple controller could potentially become an iconic style of its product system, and could distinguish a particular wrist-worn device from regular watches both by look and functionality.

Frame 3: Notification center for prompting actions with minimal distraction

Although wrist-worn devices could do and mean more than a watch, the watch analogy has been still valid in many of our graduate design explorations by viewing time as a critical experiential factor of these devices that give a reminder or prompt a user of what to do. Back to the point addressed in our focus group, as interactive systems become more pervasive and ubiquitous in our life, people more and more expect for such systems to be seamlessly weaved into their temporal and spatial context by autonomously tracking time spent on certain tasks, reminding them of what to do at a certain time, assessing their time management, and so on. The expectation is being further raised for devices to recommend a user what to do and guide him/her to do desired behaviors based on the understanding of his/her routine. Beside algorithmic approaches to such reminder or recommendation features, more persuasive and engaging forms of interventions could be explored with different materials and sensory modes of interactions (Juhlin, Zhang, Sundbom and Fernaeus,

Table 1. Innovation Matrix: mapping various meanings and technologies associated with wrist-worn devices.

2013) with minimal interruptions in foreground user activities. Beyond blindly satisfying somewhat of productivity-obsessed expectations, critical design perspectives and corresponding design cases are also in demand to speculate on healthier human-device relationships and their symbiotic interactions, as in the case of Squeezing Bracelet.

Frame 4: Statement for lifestyle changes and goal achievement

Beyond their functional features, wearable devices are also marketed as fashion items that display one's lifestyle, communities involved and values aspired to. The act of wearing an interactive device partly expresses one's personal statement that the wearer has a certain intention (e.g., fitness tracking, health monitoring, time management) and s/he is committed to it. Especially, by wearing a tracker or reminder device, a wearer is not only informed of their behavior patterns by the device, but also influenced by his/her commitment represented by the device. In addition, social recognition of the user's intention through the device could lead to support from others. Related design implications could be furthered discussed in terms of persuasive technology, fashion, and emotional attachment to a wearable device, opening up more design opportunities toward personalized meanings and interactions of wearable devices (Tsaknaki, Fernaeus and Jonsson, 2015) and social communities augmented by wearable systems (Kortuem and Segall, 2003). Such emphasis on personal values and community support enabled by wearable technologies could empower individuals to better understand who they are and what they aspire to based on informed self-awareness, guided self-reflection and connected support, thus to make impactful changes in their life and society.

Conclusion

This paper reflected on the forms and meanings of wrist-worn devices based on the review of trending issues about current wrist-worn products and our design explorations conducted as student projects. The insights from the trend survey and the design explorations are compared to identify gaps and overlaps between wearable design in the wild and in a design studio. The reflection is led to propose nuanced conceptual frames by making connections between various experiential and functional values and formal and technological components of wrist-worn devices. Our contribution lies in deconstructing mixed meanings and functional elements of wrist-worn devices, which were mostly imposed by traditional watches, and realigning them into a reflective design framework. In doing so, we also highlight challenges and opportunities for exploring new forms and meanings of wrist-worn devices that could support connected and mediated human experience with augmented digital systems. We expect the proposed framework could serve as a foundation for future design explorations by connecting wearable design study and practice and that the framework could be further expanded and consolidated by more exploratory design cases.

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References

- Ahn, Y., Hwang, S., Yoon, H., Gim, H. and Ryu, J. (2015). BandSense: Pressure-sensitive Multi-touch Interaction on a Wristband. In *Extended Abstracts of the International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 251 – 254.
- Bernaerts, Y., Druwé, M., Steensels, S., Vermeulen, J. and Schöning, J. (2014). The Office Smartwatch – Development and Design of a Smartwatch App to Digitally Augment Interactions in an Office Environment. In *Proc. of the companion publication on Designing interactive systems (DIS Companion)*. ACM 41 - 44.
- Bumgardner, B. Do fitness wearables live up to their promise? – CBS News (2015, June 24). <http://tinyurl.com/o6zcv8>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Cool Wearable. (2014). Hotblack Smartwatch Displays Football Match Results, <http://tinyurl.com/ot3r56r>, (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Dijk, J., Lugt, R. and Hummels, C. (2014). Beyond distributed representation: embodied cognition design supporting socio-sensorimotor couplings et al and their analysis of embodied theories for design. *Proc. of the International Conference on Tangible, Embodied and Embedded Interaction*. ACM, 181 - 188.
- Doppel – Set your pace, <http://www.doppel.london> (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Dunne, A. and Raby, F. (2013). *Speculative Everything: Design, Fiction, and Social Dreaming*. MIT Press.
- Einarson, E. (2013). Go Bionic With These Wearable Arduino Projects - WIRED, <http://tinyurl.com/qha3xdk>, (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Fitbit – Activity trackers and more, <https://www.fitbit.com>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Friedman, V. (2015). Adam Selman, Rihanna's Favorite Designer, Enters the Wearable War – NYTimes (Oct 27, 2015). <http://tinyurl.com/o3zqjc>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Levy, H. (2015). Top 10 Technology Trends Signal the Digital Mesh – Gartner (Oct 7, 2015). <http://tinyurl.com/oc5ulmn>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Lineable – Let's protect our kids together. <http://lineable.net/>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).

- Lyons, K. (2015). What can a dumb watch teach a smartwatch?: informing the design of smartwatches. In *Proc. of the International Symposium on Wearable Computers (ISCW)*. ACM, 3 – 10.
- Hallnäs, L. and Redström, J. (2001). Slow Technology: Designing for Reflection, *Journal of Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 5(3), 201 – 212.
- Holmquist, L. E. (2012). *Grounded Innovation: Strategies for Creating Digital Products*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- Höök, K., Ståhl, A., Jonsson, M., Mercurio, J., Karlsson, A. and Johnson, E. (2015). COVER STORY: Somaesthetic design. *interactions*. 22 (4), 26-33.
- Johnson, M. (2008). *The Meaning of The Body*. University of Chicago Press.
- Juhlin, O. (2015). Digitizing Fashion – Software for Wearable Devices. *interactions*. 22 (4), 44-47.
- Juhlin, O., Zhang, Y., Sundbom, C., and Fernaeus, Y. (2013). Fashionable Shape Switching – Explorations in Outfit-Centric Design, *Proc. of the International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 1353 - 1362.
- Jung, H., Stolterman, E., Ryan, W., Thompson, T. and Siegel, M. (2008). Toward a framework for ecologies of artifacts: how are digital artifacts interconnected within a personal life? *Proc. Of Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (NordCHI)*, 201 – 210, ACM.
- Kapture Audio-Recording Wristband Device, <http://kaptureaudio.com> (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Kessler, S. Why Technology Isn't Truly Wearable? – Fast Company (2014, October 8), <http://tinyurl.com/l78frjp>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Kortuem, G. and Segall, Z. (2003). Wearable Communities: Augmenting Social Networks with Wearable Computers. *IEEE Pervasive Computing* 2, 1 (January 2003). 71 – 78.
- Norman, D. and Verganti, A. (2014). Incremental and Radical Innovation: Design Research vs. Technology and Meaning Change. *Design Issues* 30, 1 (Winter 2014), 78 – 96.
- MOOV – The world's most advanced fitness wearable, <http://welcome.moov.cc>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Pakhchyan, S. (2015). Cute Circuit Designs Illuminated Uniforms for Airline Easy Jet – fashioning tech (Nov 10, 2015). <http://tinyurl.com/o7vuf77>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Pederson, I. (2013). *Ready to Wear: A Rhetoric of Wearable Computers and Reality-Shifting Media*. Parlor Press.
- Pan, Y. and Stolterman, E. (2015). What if HCI Becomes a Fashion Driven Discipline? In *Proc. of the International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM, 2565 - 2568.
- Pizza, S., Brown, B., McMillan, D. and Lampinen, A. (2016). Smartwatches in vivo. In *Proc. of the International Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI)*. ACM.
- Raj, D. and Ha-Brookshire, J. E. (2015). How do they create 'Superpower'? An exploration of knowledge-creation processes and work environments in the wearable technology industry. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 9 (1), 82 – 93.
- Sanches, P., Höök, K., Vaara, E., Weymann, C., Bylund, M., Ferreira, P., Peira, N., and Sjölander, M. (2010). Mind the Body! Designing a Mobile Stress Management Application Encouraging Personal Reflection. In *Proc. of Conference on Designing Interactive Systems (DIS)*. ACM 47 – 56.
- Silina, Y. and Haddadi, H. (2015). "New Directions in Jewelry": a Close Look at Emerging Trends & Developments in Jewelry. In *Proc. of the International Symposium on Wearable Computers (ISCW)*. ACM, 43 – 56.
- Svanæs, D. (2013). Interaction design for and with the lived body: Some implications of merleau-ponty's phenomenology. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 20 (1), Article No. 8.
- Stolterman, E. & Wiberg, M. (2010). Concept-Driven Interaction Design Research, *Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 25(2), 95 — 118.
- Tsaknaki, V., Fernaeus, Y., and Jonsson, M. (2015). Precious Materials of Interaction – Exploring Interactive Accessories as Jewellery Items, *Proc. of Nordes 2015: Design Ecologies*.
- The Quantified Self: Counting Every Moment – The Economist. (2013, May 3rd), <http://tinyurl.com/7rz55me>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).
- Thompson, C. (2015). Can the Swiss Watchmaker Survive the Digital Age? - NYTimes, <http://tinyurl.com/nhoecm>, (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Vanhemert, K. (2015). *An Analogue Activity Tracker Isn't as Ridiculous as It Sounds*, <http://tinyurl.com/q5wohf2>, (Accessed July 1, 2015).
- Verganti, R. (2009). *Design Driven Innovation: Changing the Rules of Competition by Radically Innovating What Things Mean*. Harvard Business Press.
- Wagstaff, K. Data Overload: is the 'quantified self' really the future? – NBC News (2014, August 30), <http://tinyurl.com/nhus5oq>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).

Wallack, R. Wearable technology catapulting health and fitness into future – LA Times (2015, January 23), <http://tinyurl.com/pb895t2>, (Accessed Nov 11, 2015).

Xu, C. and Lyons K. 2015. Shimmering Smartwatches: Exploring the Smartwatch Design Space. *Proc. of the International Conference on Tangible, Embodied and Embedded Interaction (TEI)*. ACM, 69 - 76.